

Design of the Ultra-Low Voltage Sigma-Delta Converter in CMOS nanotechnology

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Abstract—In this text, design of fully differential (FD) first-order single-loop single-bit ultra-low voltage non-output-synchronized Sigma-Delta analog to digital converter (SD-ADC) supplied by 0.6 V is presented. The proposed SD-ADC was designed in standard 130 nm CMOS technology. The text is focused on the design of the following four blocks: difference amplifier, switched-capacitor (SC) integrator, comparator and 1-bit digital to analog converter (1-bit DAC). The principle of their design is stated in the individual chapters of this article. The highest attention is paid to the integrator, which is the main block of the analog part of the circuit. This integrator is based on two-stage Rail-to-Rail (RtR) FD operational transconductance amplifier (OTA) working in a sub-threshold regime inside and switched-capacitors as equivalent resistors forming a low pass filter on the outside. In addition, as part of the circuit, the SC common-mode feedback (CMFB) circuit was designed to minimize the offset common-mode voltage at its output.

Keywords—analog design, ultra-low voltage, Sigma-Delta, analog to digital converter, switched capacitor, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, analog designers are facing difficult challenges due to evolution of CMOS nanometer technology and continuous scaling-down of the power supply voltage of integrated circuits (IC). These things cause decreasing dimensions of transistors and affect to the properties of the analog circuits. Usage of transistors as resistors, capacitors, amplifiers or current sources is still needed in analog design but the requirement to minimize the supply voltage brings many problems. For example, more than 2 or 3 transistors cannot be stacked because of the voltage headroom issue. In addition, many of them work in weak inversion region where current I_D exponentially depends on voltage V_{GS} and where is considerable parasitic capacitance effect. On the contrary, in digital design, transistors are mostly used as the switches and there are not so many problems of this kind with them. It is one of the most important advantage of digital ICs.

ADCs has been moved to the CMOS nanometer technologies as an interface between analog and digital circuits. Both of these kinds of circuits are implemented on single chip, so they have to be power-supplied by one V_{DD} voltage. Since the digital part of the circuit can operate with an ultra-low supply voltage, the analogue parts of the circuit are adapted to these ultra-low values of V_{DD} as much as possible.

In SD-ADC is low-pass filter - integrator the main block of the analog part of the circuit. It causes the pulses to densify on the digital output signal. Compared to its input, the shape of the signal is different, but its nature is preserved [?], [?], [?].

Fig. 1 shows the block scheme of proposed fully differential SD-ADC. It is important to note, that the green labels (+) and (−) do not determine the polarity of the signal. They are used only to distinguish two mutually differential signals (shifted by phase of 180°). In this scheme, voltages V_{ref1} and V_{ref2} coming from 1-bit DAC are subtracted (by difference amplifier) from analog input signal. This modified signal is then integrated and compared to the reference voltage in comparator (in this case $V_{DD}/2$). Digital output signal from comparator sets the output voltage coming from 1-bit DAC back to the difference amplifier at the input. [?].

Fig. 1. The FD first-order single-loop non-output-synchronized SD-ADC

Fig. 2 shows ideal outputs from each block in the Fig.1. These outputs illustrate only single path of the differential signal (for example (+)).

Fig. 2. Ideal outputs from blocks of single path of differential signal of proposed SD-ADC

In this paper, the principle of the converter design is introduced in section II (integrator), III (comparator), IV (1-bit DAC) and V (difference amplifier). The achieved results obtained from simulations are stated in section VI and the evaluation of all process is summarized in the last section VII.

II. PROPOSED INTEGRATOR

Topology of the integrator block from Fig. 1 is introduced in the Fig. 3 based on the SC technique. Clock signals in Fig. 3 are generating non-overlapping signals to switch capacitors i_C_{S1} - i_C_{S4} and internal capacitors in CMFB circuit.

Fig. 3. Topology of FD SC integrator

A. Operational transconductance amplifier - OTA

The topology of OTA is shown in the Fig. 4. This circuit is based on parallel connection of two-stage NMOS and PMOS operational amplifiers (OPAMPs) working in sub-threshold regimes.

Fig. 4. Topology of OTA

Complementary connection of NMOS and PMOS in the OPAMP output stage allows RrR operation at output. It is well-known that input voltage range of PMOS transistor is limited from above by the voltage:

$$V_{PMOS_{MAX}} = V_{DD} - |V_{DS_{sat}}(i_{MP7})| - |V_{TH}(i_{MP1})| \quad (1)$$

In the range from $V_{PMOS_{MAX}}$ to V_{DD} is NMOS transistor active only. Contrariwise, the input voltage range of NMOS transistor is limited from below by the voltage:

$$V_{NMOS_{MIN}} = V_{DS_{sat}}(i_{MN8}) + V_{TH}(i_{MN1}) \quad (2)$$

In the range from ground to $V_{NMOS_{MIN}}$ is PMOS transistor active only.

The input transistors (i_{MN1} , i_{MN2} , i_{MP1} , i_{MP2}) was set to the sub-threshold region by the equations:

$$V_{eff} = 2 \cdot V_T \cdot n \cdot \ln(\exp(\sqrt{IF}) - 1) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{W}{L} = \frac{I_D}{I_{D0} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{V_{eff}}{n \cdot V_T}\right)} \quad (4)$$

The current sources (i_{MP7} , i_{MN8}) works in strong saturation by the V_{DS} voltage approximately 100 mV. Transistors i_{MN7} , i_{MN9} and i_{MP8} was used as the simple current mirrors for circuit biasing. i_{MP4} , i_{MP5} , i_{MN4} and i_{MN5} was used as a current mirrors for output stage 1 and 2 [?].

As an output stage, AB class amplifier is used. Dimensions of the transistors i_{MP3} , i_{MN3} , i_{MP6} and i_{MN6} was designed for relatively high currents in that branches due to driving output capacitors and capacitors in SC CMFB circuit.

B. Clock-boosting circuit

In order to control switching transistors in CMFB circuit clock-boosting circuit was used. Its topology is shown in the Fig. 5. Two inverters at the beginning of the circuit modify the rising and the falling edges of the clock signal for better operate with. Cross-coupled NMOS transistors b_{MN1} and b_{MN2} together with the capacitors b_{C1} and b_{C2} are forming a charge pump. Pulses from the clock are shifted up by adding V_{DD} voltage to them. By the transistors b_{MN3} and b_{MN4} is this shifted voltage (in the other words: shifted charge) connected to a "bootstrap" capacitor b_{C3} . By switching the transistors b_{MP1} , b_{MN5} , b_{MP2} , b_{MN6} , b_{MN7} , b_{MN8} and b_{MN9} is mentioned charge transported to the output - switching transistor in SC CMFB circuit. This circuit was designed as a part of SC CMFB circuit as a "bootstrap" [2].

Fig. 5. Topology of clock-boost circuit

C. Switched-capacitor CMFB circuit

Fig. 6 shows the topology of the CMFB circuit. There are three task for CMFB circuit: sensing the common mode outputs $i_{V_{OUT+}}$ and $i_{V_{OUT-}}$ from fully differential OTA, comparison of the sensed results with a reference voltage V_{CM} (in this design, the reference voltage for CMFB circuit is equal to $V_{DD}/2$) and return the bias voltage V_{BIAS} back to the OTA by CMFB output. This switched CMFB circuit is clocked by non-overlapping pulses with frequency $f_{sw} = 20$ MHz. These pulses are shifted up in "bootstrap" circuits for better gate-switching of all the transistors in the Fig. 6 [2]. All the transistors have been designed with the same dimensions as a switches with a low enough R_{ON} parameter.

The capacitors cm_C_1 (cm_C_2) and cm_C_3 (cm_C_4) have been designed with a ratio k :

$$k = \frac{cm_C_1}{cm_C_3} = \frac{cm_C_2}{cm_C_4} \quad (5)$$

In order to obtain low value of output offset, the ratio of these capacitors should be perfectly set. However, cm_C_1 (cm_C_2) can not be too large, because OTA will not be able to drive them. On the contrary, cm_C_2 (cm_C_4) can not be too small, because the parasitic capacitance of the switching transistors will start to affect the circuit. Transistors cm_M_{P1} , cm_M_{P2} , cm_M_{N9} and cm_M_{N10} form the output invertors for driving the switched CMFB outputs. These outputs are connected to the OTA, as is shown in the Fig. 3.

Fig. 6. Topology of switched CMFB circuit

D. Switching transmission gates (T-gates)

As it is shown in the Fig 3., capacitors i_C_{S1} - i_C_{S4} are switched with transmission gates (T-gates) i_T_1 - i_T_8 for better charge transport. For initial values of capacitors, voltage gain and cutoff frequency the following equations can be used:

$$C_{sw} \propto \frac{1}{f_{sw} \cdot R_{eq}} \quad (6)$$

$$A_{INT_MAX} \propto \frac{i_C_{S1}}{i_C_{S3}} \quad (7)$$

$$f_{cutoff} = BW_{INT} \propto \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot i_C_1 \cdot R_{eq}(i_C_{S2})} \quad (8)$$

III. PROPOSED COMPARATOR

Topology of the comparator block from Fig. 1 is introduced in the Fig. 7. The main parameter of this block is slew-rate, which can be calculated by equation:

$$SR = \frac{I_D}{C_L} \quad (9)$$

Due to this fact, this topology is based on two-stage NMOS OPAMP, which is formed by transistors c_M_{N1} , c_M_{N2} , c_M_{P1} , c_M_{P2} and c_M_{P4} as a

first stage and c_M_{P3} and c_M_{N5} as a second stage. Transistor c_M_{N3} is used as a simple current mirror for circuit biasing. To achieve the highest possible SR parameter, there was three invertors designed at the output as the amplifiers that are formed by transistors c_M_{P4} , c_M_{P5} , c_M_{P6} , c_M_{N6} , c_M_{N7} . and c_M_{N8} .

Single output from the integrator is connected to the c_V_{IN} input. The V_{REF} input is connected to a $V_{DD}/2$ voltage, what was mentioned in introduction.

Fig. 7. Topology of comparator

IV. PROPOSED 1-BIT DAC

The topology of the 1-bit DAC block from Fig. 1 is introduced in the Fig. 8. This block is the most simple part of the whole proposed circuit. It is formed by single inverter (used as a switch made from transistors dac_M_{N1} and dac_M_{P1}) and two T-gates dac_T_1 and dac_T_2 .

When *logic 1* is at the input of this block, voltage V_{ref2} is set to the output. On the contrary, when *logic 0* is at the input, voltage V_{ref1} is set to the output.

Fig. 8. Topology of 1-bit DAC

V. PROPOSED DIFFERENCE AMPLIFIER

The topology of the difference amplifier block from Fig. 1 is introduced in the Fig. 10. This block is based on single-stage PMOS OPAMP and the resistors set for subtracting operation. The topology of PMOS OPAMP is shown in the Fig. 9. Transistors $diff_M_{P1}$, $diff_M_{P2}$, $diff_M_{N1}$, $diff_M_{N2}$ and $diff_M_{P4}$ form the OPAMP. Again, transistor $diff_M_{P3}$ is used as a simple current mirror for circuit biasing.

The main task of this block is the signal subtracting and it can be obtained by following equation:

$$diff_V_{OUT} = \frac{R_f}{R_1} (SAI - diff_V_{IN}) \quad (10)$$

Of course, $R_1 = R_2 = R_f = R_g$ and the gain of this block is equal to 1 (or 0 [dB]).

Fig. 9. Topology of inner PMOS OPAMP form difference amplifier

Fig. 10. Topology of difference amplifier

VI. ACHIEVED RESULTS

The integrator has been simulated with the signals of varying frequencies, amplitudes and types. For DC simulation of the OTA (with disconnected CMFB circuit), the input voltage was swept in the range of GND and V_{DD} . In the AC simulation, two periodic sources with 180 degrees phase shift were used for simulate differential input signal. Because of using clocks, periodic steady-state analysis (PSS analysis) and periodic AC analysis (PAC analysis) was used. In the Fig. 11 are shown the transfer responses of inverting and non-inverting outputs, where R_tR output voltage range can be obtained. Fig. 12 shows frequency response of OTA with maximum gain of 46.16 dB. Bandwidth of proposed OTA is 24.23 kHz, while gain-bandwidth is 5.03 MHz.

Fig. 11. Transfer response of TA

Fig. 12. Frequency and phase response of TA

Fig. 13 shows frequency response of whole integrator where low-frequency gain of 24.09 dB and cutoff frequency 165.95 kHz were achieved.

Fig. 13. Frequency and phase response of integrator

In Fig. 14 is shown time response of integrator to a harmonic input signal and Fig. 15 shows time response of integrator to a pulse input signal.

Fig. 14. Harmonic signal response - integration

Fig. 15. Pulse signal response - integration

All the achieved integrator parameters are summarized in the Tab. 1.

TABLE I. INTEGRATOR PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
V_{DD}	0.6 V
C_{LOAD}	10 pF
A_{OTA_MAX}	46.16 dB
BW_{OTA}	24.23 kHz
GBW_{OTA}	5.03 MHz
PM_{OTA}	81.53°
A_{INT_MAX}	24.09 dB
BW_{INT}	165.95 kHz
GBW_{INT}	1.43 MHz

The following figures was made by simulation of harmonic differential signal with amplitude 15 mV and frequency 50 kHz . In the Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 are shown (+) and (-) outputs from difference amplifiers. On the both characteristics the operations of subtraction the voltage values V_{ref1} and V_{ref2} are visible.

Fig. 16. Difference amplifier output (+)

Fig. 17. Difference amplifier output (-)

In the Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 are shown (+) and (-) outputs from SC integrator. On the both characteristics the integral operations of signals from Fig. 16 and Fig. 17 are visible.

Fig. 18. SC integrator output (+)

Fig. 19. SC integrator output (-)

In the Fig. 20 and Fig. 21 are shown analog differential input signal and (+) and (-) outputs from comparator - the main output from SD-ADC. The values over 300 mV from Fig. 18 and Fig. 19 are evaluated as *logic 1*, the values under 300 mV from mentioned pictures are evaluated as *logic 0*.

Fig. 20. SD-ADC (comparator) output (+)

Fig. 21. SD-ADC (comparator) output (-)

In the Fig. 22 and Fig. 23 are shown (+) and (-) outputs from looped 1-bit DAC. Voltage $V_{ref1} = 15\text{ mV}$, voltage $V_{ref2} = -15\text{ mV}$.

Fig. 22. 1-bit DAC output (+)

Fig. 23. 1-bit DAC output (–)

VII. CONCLUSION

The fully differential first-order single-loop single-bit ultra-low voltage non-output-synchronized Sigma-Delta analog to digital converter supplied by 0.6 V was designed. It is based on SC integrator with bandwidth 165.95 kHz and it is the upper limit of frequencies that SD-ADC can be used.

If necessary, gain 24.09 dB can be increased by larger capacitors ratio (7). It is important to note, that for possibly increase the gain, it is necessary to design output stages for higher current values.

This converter was developed mainly for on-chip energy-harvesting applications (solar panels, wind power stations etc.).

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